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A TV Recommender System Using Ratings

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ABSTRACT

Over the past few years, technology has impacted heavily in the distribution of television content. Users have been treated with an overload of content easily accessible on many platforms such as TV, PC's, phones or any hand-held devices. However, these overloaded contents have presented a challenge where viewers are unable to make informed content selections. Unfortunately, TV content providers do not pay too much attention to serving tailor-made contents as much as they do to content listing. The user's viewing experience will be much greater with systems that suggest contents best suited for every user. Researchers have adopted sentiment analysis, content-based filtering and collaborative filtering for personalized TV. Even though these approaches make content selection easier, they do not yield same results with their recommendations. As a result, one approach will not work perfectly for different group of users. In this article, content recommendation system is proposed to provide a better viewing experience for TV viewers using three main solutions. A rating system that allows viewers express their opinions about a show, a content-based recommendation filtering, and a collaborative filtering. The fusion of these three solutions is to ensure that all viewers queries are satisfied once and for all. The proposed content assistant algorithm will form the main part of this article where the system is discussed in detail. The results show that centered cosine similarity identifies and performs recommendations accurately. The system evaluation and testing is provided to support the concept. And finally, a conclusion is drawn to prove why this method serves customers needs better.

Keywords

Recommender systems, Content-based filtering, Collaborative filtering, Hybrid filtering, TV show.

Introduction

The growth of television is undoubtedly giving us more options with where you can watch TV, which device to use, what to watch, and many more. Today, technology has made it possible to use mobile phones, tablets, etc. to watch TV on the go. With thousands of amazing channels to choose from, viewers are presented with an overload of contents making selection difficult and time consuming. Hence, the need for personalized TV content is crucial today than ever. With the help of AI and machine learning, many industries have adopted personalized recommendation systems. In Social media platforms, content is suggested to you based on your location and previous searches.

It has been found that the personalized recommendation services have been used widely to increase sales and customer satisfaction in e-commerce (Zhou et.al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2014) [1], where these systems help to deal with the problem of information overload by filtering vital information fragment out of the large amount to generate information according to user's preferences and interests (Konstan & Riedl, 2012) [3]. Personalizing content in TV means the viewer spends less time browsing through all the channels to find what might interest him/her. It also helps TV content providers to produce contents that are tailor-made for every user to generate maximum satisfaction. The current television does not allow user interactivity. The proposed system will outline this and other TV related problems and provide solutions.

Recommendation systems make things easier. According to Mulvenna et al. [13], the basic goal of personalization systems is to provide users with what they want or need without requiring them to ask for it explicitly. From a business standpoint, the more relevant products a user finds on the platform, the higher their engagement. This often results in increased revenue for the platform itself. Various sources say that as much as 35–40% of tech giants' revenue comes from recommendations alone.

To ensure that recommendations have better accuracy, a hybrid filtering of content-based and collaborative filtering is merged to provide the best prediction to TV user. Hybrid filtering allows both content-based and collaborative filtering to complement each other in terms of their drawbacks.

Overview of Recommender Systems

Recommendation systems are applications from data science research that deals with serving tailor-made contents to users based on the preference they attach to their selection of items. The 'items' ranges from many types of commodities such as products in the supermarket, e-commerce, online movie platforms, social media feeds etc. Most global e-commerce platforms such as Amazon, Alibaba etc. have adopted recommendation systems to boost sales and enhance convenience for customers. On Facebook, recommender systems are used to suggest friends and posts that have a higher chance of being of interest to the target user. Netflix is arguably the platform where recommendation system is used most effectively. The main concept of recommender systems is to identify user interest, predict their future preference and suggest these contents to them.

Recommendation systems can be described simply as the filtering of information for easy access to a target group. Recommendation systems can be classified into three main parts:

Content-based Filtering: This is providing content for users based on their previously rated shows. It is based on the contents the user has previously shown interest in by means of liking a button or rating the content. At times, a series of questions are provided for new users to determine their preference before contents are suggested to them. This is also another form of content-based filtering. Content-based system has many advantages as well as disadvantages in its application. It is important to note that one of the main objectives of content recommendation is to reduce overloaded content and content-based filtering works perfectly when the user does more ratings. With this, the system will fine tune contents based on the user's preference and reduce content overload. Also, making recommendations to users based on their explicit information will serve users with accurate tailor-made contents.

Collaborative Filtering: This is providing contents for users based on others interest. The system identifies other users who have similar preference to the target user and then recommend their rated shows to the target user. Collaborative filtering has huge dependency on the users input to build a group of similar users for recommendation. In instances where there are not many ratings from the active user or similar users, there is a higher chance of inaccuracies in suggested contents. For collaborative filtering to produce higher accuracy, there is a crucial need for more ratings from target user and similar users. Collaborative filtering suffers what is termed the "cold start". The cold start is caused by new users in the system which have not submitted any ratings. Without any information about the user the system is not able to guess the user's preferences and generate recommendations until a few items have been rated [8]. There are two main types of collaborative filtering techniques. These are based on how the recommendation are made. If the system uses items to find other similar items and recommend them to the user because they have liked the target item, it is referred to as an *item-item based collaborative* filtering technique. However, if the system is designed to identify other similar users and then recommend their liked items to the target user, it is referred to as a *user-user collaborative filtering*.

Hybrid Filtering: The hybrid filtering, a merger of content-based and collaborative filtering techniques has been hugely successful compared to any of the two above. This is because while content-based narrows the search down to preferred items only, the collaborative filtering will suggest extra contents that have a higher chance of being of interest to the target user.

Literature Review

A study of existing TV recommendation systems show that researchers have used content-based filtering approach, collaborative filtering approach, and sentiment analysis techniques in assisting viewers' content

selection over the past decade. It is important to note that even though these different approaches serve the common objective of personalized content recommendations, they do not provide the same results of a complete solution. The users' lack of a better TV viewing experience cannot be coupled into a one problem case. And this is why different researchers have identified different problems and have suggested different approaches to solving these problems.

With *content-based filtering*, a questionnaire is used to acquire information from a user and this information is used to suggest personalized content. Hence, recommendations are made only by the implicit and explicit input of the user in focus. The basic information that is required for content-based filtering or mostly age, gender, a genre of channels, time the user wants to watch. According to [5], a personalized recommendation is a process of collecting and storing information about website visits, handling the digital content assets, analyzing user profiles, analyzing current and past user behavior and interaction, including delivery of the right content to each user. According to [6], two characteristics bring up new challenges. First, the timing of recommendation becomes important in the TV recommender system. Suppose a favorite movie of a user is just started on a channel while the user is watching a plain show. Then, it will be good timing for a recommendation for the user. However, users do not know when is good timing to demand a recommendation because they do not know what shows are currently available on other channels. Therefore, the recommender system needs to catch the timing to recommend as well as deciding what to recommend.

According to [5], in many cases, users are looking for things that might interest them, but do not have concrete desideration in mind when browsing a Website. In such cases, it is a recommendation engine that presents the most plausible content that the user may want, based on her interests as demonstrated by her *past activities*.

According to Peter Forbes et al. [12] Recommendations for movies on Netflix are based on movies a user likes or dislikes. Based on the movies you liked and disliked, we have found users of similar tastes. Since they liked the following movies, we think you may like them too, even though we have no idea what types of movies they are.

With Live TV, contents shown on the TV are usually not what the users ask for. Hence, recommending shows for a user based on only his/her preference would limit the content suggestion to very few shows. And this will not be the best experience for many users. And so, researchers have gone beyond and suggested content based on other users' interests by identifying users with similar preferences. This is simply called collaborative filtering. In Lekakos, G., & Giaglis, G. (2002) [15]: Personalizing advertisements, i.e. providing viewers with messages that they are most likely to be interested in, offers marketers the opportunity to increase the accuracy of their targeting, while at the same time providing viewers with messages that increase their satisfaction in terms of interest in the advertised product.

Time-stamp STB's - TV service providers made set-top-box that records time-stamp of users viewing habit. A time-stamp is a time-based history of every activity that takes place on the user's device. It records and indicates the time the user spends on each channel and every other activity such as turn-on, turn-off, record, playback etc. DSTV, a company that provides satellite TV in most part of Africa inserted a chip in their set-top box to capture viewers activity log with time-stamp to enable them analyze viewers preference and behavior. This was aimed at creating tailor-made contents suitable for their clients.

Dovile T (2017) proposed an IoT TV in the article, Internet of Things (IoT) driven media recommendations for television viewers [17]. The IoT TV media content recommendations are based on data gathered from smart devices and systems connected with OTT television. Firstly, smart wearables provide information to OTT television about a person's stress levels and this information is taken into consideration when making media content recommendations. Secondly, living in smart cities sensors communicate with media streaming devices about how much time viewers are going to spend on their way. According to this information, viewers see media content recommendations that optimally match with their commuting time. Thirdly, media content suggestions are based on information collected from smart home appliances. For instance, an oven "speaks" with an OTT television platform to tailor media content recommendations according to how much spare time is left until a dinner is ready. According to Dovile, the concept of an IoT TV could be realized based on the above factors.

In the paper "Whats's on TV tonight" [8], a hybrid filtering of content-based and collaborative filtering was proposed for Queveo 2.0 TV. The system implements collaborative filtering, content-based filtering, and a merging algorithm that combines the results provided by both methods above. In content-based, users are asked explicit questions to build profiles for them. These questions include; age, gender, profession, free time etc. The CF algorithm can be viewed as a generalized CF approach which utilizes SVD as an augmenting technique in order to enhance the recommender system's efficiency and improve the accuracy of the generated predictions. The CF approach makes use of memory-based user-to-user correlation, as the user neighborhood for a new user has to be computed during runtime of the system. The system also uses memory-based user-to-item correlation to predict the level of interest for each item and calculate the items' neighborhood [8].

A methodology of personalized recommendation system on mobile device for digital television viewers by Chumsak Sibunruang and Jantima Polpinij [4]. Personal information of users is collected through questionnaire, explicitly. A profile is created for every user based on the information gathered through questionnaire. A search is performed on the web to identify shows that will interest a user. These shows are collected and stored with their description such as title, genre, cast etc. A second search is done but this time on the TV through the Electronic program guide (EPG) to find similar shows as the ones retrieved from the web. After having required annotation of each TV program, it is used as being of TV viewer's interest, and then the system searches for other TV programs that are similar based on comparison of this TV program annotation. Finally, a collection of favorite programs will be collected as a list of personal TV programs. The

main technique used to find similar TV programs is called Content-based Similarity Analysis (CBSA) (Pazzani, & Billsus, 2007) [18]. CBSA applies machine learning algorithms as the key mechanism for content-based analysis. Then, these algorithms generally learn a function that creates the model of each user's interests. By using the model, it helps to predict the new program that user would be interested.

Problem statement

Over the last few years, research into recommender systems have seen rapid growth in media consumption. Most of these researches are channeled towards video on-demand (VOD) contents such as movies, series, pre-recorded videos. Not much can be said about Live TV shows as much as the on-demand videos. Because of this, recommendation for TV shows are not so common and TV users have to deal with overly loaded contents.

Also, with high internet speed coupled with smart devices, it has become very easy to watch TV on the go anywhere at all times. Hence, TV service providers have developed over-the-top mobile TV's for their subscribers. However, these mobile TV's are clones of the big TV's and they offer no recommendations to users. They are made of long list of TV channels where users have to go through to find their interested contents. Some mobile TV's have a "favorite" section for users where they can add their most-liked channels to make it easier to find. This also creates a new disadvantage where users become too comfortable exploring within a small group of favorite channels when there could be many other channels that would be of interest to them. When users cut down their list of channels, they become disinterested in trying new contents. It is in the best interest of TV service providers to get their users to explore more contents on their TV.

Proposed solution

Based on the problems detailed above, this system is proposing a hybrid filtering approach of content-based and collaborative to recommend TV channels to users. This system will accept users input in the form of ratings for content recommendation. Therefore, if a user rates shows, the system will rely on the content-based algorithm to recommend similar shows while the collaborative filtering will identify similar users and recommend their rated shows to the target user. Both approaches have advantages that complement the disadvantages of the other and vice-versa. For example:

1. *First time rater*: This is a situation where a target user is new to the system and has not rated enough items and so the system is unable to gather enough data on them to predict their interests accurately. In this instance, collaborative filtering becomes redundant or works poorly and therefore the system relies on content-based to recommend contents through user-content profiling.

2. *Cold start*: This is when the system does not have enough users who have rated shows and so it becomes difficult to create neighbors for the target user for recommendations. This is a special problem associated with

collaborative filtering because collaborative filtering relies on the ratings of other users to predict items to the target user. It is also used to describe the situation where the target user is new to the system and has not rated enough shows and hence the system is unable to find similar users to the target user.

3. Sparsity: This describes zero entries in a table and the difficulty associated with making recommendations. Some users tend to rate items poorly and so it becomes difficult for the system to accurately profile them for better recommendation. To accurately recommend contents to users in this circumstance, the system relies on content-based filtering using explicit data as inputs. For example, asking series of questions from the user to determine their interests.

System Architecture

The hybrid filtering will combine both content-based and collaborative techniques. The content-based will identify similar shows to previously rated ones of the target user and make recommendations. The collaborative filtering will apply a user-user technique to suggest channels to the target user. Both recommendations will be presented to the user without prioritization.

Figure 1: A System Architecture of Hybrid Filtering

Methodology

Datasets for the content-based filtering project was acquired from <https://www.kaggle.com/PromptCloudHQ/imdb-data>, a dataset of 1000 popular movies over 10 years. The

dataset consists of movies released on or before July 2016. This dataset captures feature points like: Title, Genre, Description, Director, Actors, Year, Runtime, Rating, Votes, Revenue, Metascore.

For the collaborative filtering we need two tables of data, a table of TV shows and description and a table of user ratings. The dataset is acquired from <https://grouplens.org/datasets/movielens/latest/>. GroupLens is a research group in the department of computer science and engineering at the university of Minnesota. There are two very important tables needed for this collaborative filtering algorithm, namely: movies and ratings.

Content-based Filtering: In this section, Centered Cosine Similarity for identifying similar items will be discussed. In content-based filtering, recommendations are made to a target user using two main inputs, user previous ratings and user profiling. This section will focus on user previous ratings for content recommendation with cosine similarity.

For us to determine how similar two shows are, we will use cosine similarity

Let's create a utility matrix for User A based on 5 shows with features that describe them. We will provide ratings from a scale of 1-5 based on how much in-depth it falls under each category.

		Features				
	TV show	Kids rated	Adult rated	Comedy	Educational	Religious
A	People and places	1	4	4	5	3
B	Champs league	2	4	1	2	1
C	MTV awards	1	4	2	2	1
D	Rise of the Guardian	5	1	1	2	1
E	90's Hip Hop	1	4	1	2	1

Table 1. An illustration of a TV show with characteristics and ratings.

Analyzing the table shows some similarities between certain shows. Most noticeably, D and F with same ratings for 4 out of 5.

Cosine similarity:

$$\text{similarity}(A,B) = \frac{A \cdot B}{\|A\| \times \|B\|} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i \times B_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i^2} \times \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n B_i^2}} \quad (1)$$

$\text{Similarity}(C,E) = 0.981433$. Cosine similarity shows how closer C and E are.

$\text{Similarity}(A,D) = 0.561514$. Cosine similarity shows how dissimilar A and D are just as seen in the table.

So, we must put a threshold to determine which shows to recommend to the target user. To ensure we recommend highly similar contents, we will set the threshold at 0.8. Anything above that will be recommended and below that will not be recommended.

Collaborative Filtering: The system will use K-Nearest Neighbor cosine similarity to identify similar users to the target user for content recommendation. Hence, this system will adapt user-user based model. In performing a recommendation for TV users, it is important to expand the neighboring territories so that the system can rely on more data for recommendations. An item-item based filtering will only recommend contents that are similar to what the target user has rated in the past. Even though research shows that item-item based approach has better accuracy, this system is aimed at recommending most-liked shows to the user. This system takes explicit information from users in the form of ratings, on a scale of 0-5. The system will identify similar users called *neighbors*, neighbors are users who have the same interests as the target user and have shown interest by rating similar contents positively.

Let's create a utility matrix of 5 users who have rated 7 TV shows:

	TV1	TV2	TV3	TV4	TV5	TV6	TV7
A	4			5	1		
B	5	5	4				
C				2	4	5	
D		3					3
E	5	4	4				

Table 2. A matrix of 5 users ratings of 7 shows

To find the similarities between two users, we first have to *normalize*, and center each rating. This is known as centered cosine similarity. The average ratings of the users:

$(i_1+i_2+\dots+i_n)/n$, n is the number of ratings given. In this case 3.

So for User A, $(4+5+1)/3=3.3$

For User B, $(5+5+4)/3=4.6666$

For User C, $(2+4+5)/3=3.666$

For User D, $(3+3)/2=3$.

For User E, $(5+4+4)/3=4.33$

Now, we subtract the normalized ratings from the actual ratings given. And our new table looks like:

	TV1	TV2	TV3	TV4	TV5	TV6	TV7
A	0.7			1.7	-2.3		
B	0.333	0.333	-0.667				
C				-1.66	0.334	1.33	
D		0					0
E	0.67	-0.33	-0.33				

Table 3. A normalized matrix of 5 users ratings of 7 shows

$$similarity(A,B) = \frac{A \cdot B}{\|A\| \times \|B\|} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i \times B_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i^2} \times \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n B_i^2}} \quad (2)$$

$Similarity(B,E) = 0.5$. This shows huge similarity between these two users.

$Similarity(A,C) = -0.56$. Cosine similarity shows how dissimilar A and C are.

Conclusion

This paper has implemented a hybrid filtering of both content-based and collaborative filtering for better TV viewing experience. The concept of an interactive TV is based on the recommendations to users from this proposed system. The datasets were collected and analyzed carefully to satisfy scientific standards. Recommendation in content-based was mainly based on user previous rating data. And the collaborative technique was a user-user based approach to find similar users. The accuracy of the content-based and collaborative algorithm is shown in both results with the centered cosine similarity computation.

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